

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-33

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-33

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0042 A	Wavelength=1.54184	
Cell:	a=49.7043(14)	b=49.7043(14)	c=15.3050(5)
	alpha=90	beta=90	gamma=120
Temperature:	140 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	32746(2)	32746(2)	
Space group	R -3	R -3	
Hall group	-R 3	-R 3	
Moiety formula	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, C20 H40 K O8 [+ solvent]	C30 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, C20 H40 K O8	
Sum formula	C50 H74 B2 Co K N6 O14 [+ solvent]	C50 H74 B2 Co K N6 O14	
Mr	1102.80	1102.80	
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.007	1.007	
Z	18	18	
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	2.788	2.788	
F000	10512.0	10512.0	
F000'	10507.47		
h,k,lmax	61,61,18	60,57,18	
Nref	14547	14044	
Tmin,Tmax	0.846,0.885	0.257,1.000	
Tmin'	0.118		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.257 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 0.965 Theta(max)= 73.048

R(reflections)= 0.0467(9245) wR2(reflections)= 0.1094(14044)

S = 0.964 Npar= 732

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT230_ALERT_2_C	Hirshfeld Test Diff for	O13	--C45	.	6.5 s.u.
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C	Low	'MainMol'	Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of		K1 Check
PLAT905_ALERT_3_C	Negative K value in the Analysis of Variance ...				-0.482 Report
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600			109 Report

● **Alert level G**

PLAT002_ALERT_2_G	Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite				11 Note
PLAT003_ALERT_2_G	Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ...				10 Report
PLAT063_ALERT_4_G	Crystal Size Possibly too Large for Beam Size ..			0.77 mm	
PLAT176_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SADI Records				3 Report
PLAT178_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SIMU Records				2 Report
PLAT301_ALERT_3_G	Main Residue Disorder	(Resd 1)			4% Note
PLAT302_ALERT_4_G	Anion/Solvent/Minor-Residue Disorder (Resd 2)				17% Note
PLAT606_ALERT_4_G	Solvent Accessible VOID(S) in Structure				! Info
PLAT720_ALERT_4_G	Number of Unusual/Non-Standard Labels				4 Note
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Co1	(III)			3.12 Info
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints				158 Note
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G	No Info/Value for _atom_sites_solution_primary .				Please Do !
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).				1 Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600			380 Note
PLAT913_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF				1 Note
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G	Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity				3.8 Low
PLAT951_ALERT_5_G	Calculated (ThMax) and CIF-Reported Kmax Differ				4 Units
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.				2 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
4 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
18 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

1 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
5 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
7 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
7 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/09/2020; check.def file version of 20/08/2020

